

IKEJA BAR REVIEW

A publication of the Nigerian Bar Association, Ikeja Branch.
Vol. 2, Part 1, Sept. 2007

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Editor-in-Chief
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PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES OF CBN'S
MICROFINANCE REGULATORY AND SUPERVISORY
FRAMEWORK ON SME'S IN NIGERIA

K.A Adeyemo
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INTRODUCTION

Many countries are now addressing the issue of how best to broaden the reach of financial services to those segments of the population that have been, historically, "unbanked" or "underbanked". A central element of the promotion of inclusive financial systems is the development of micro-finance which implies the provision of financial services such as loans, savings instruments and payment functions at affordable cost to individuals and groups that have typically been excluded from the organized financial system due to their limited means and low economic status. About 80 percent of people in developing countries derive their incomes from the informal sector, there is thus the need for good financial sector infrastructures in support of international and national strategies to reduce income poverty by half. In many developing countries, Nigeria inclusive, women constitute the majority of micro-entrepreneurs in the informal economy and a significant percentage of the formal sector. Many of them are illiterate, and live in poor rural communities. Setting up their own enterprises, is usually the only possible way to be employed and earn income on their own. Frequently, the only option to access capital is through illegal moneylenders who charge high rates and lend only small sums relative to the needs of a growing enterprise. Because of the interconnectivity between financial power, poverty and women, micro-finance has an active role in improving economic equality. Increased economic power enables women to improve other areas of their own lives and their children's¹

This paper examines the concept of Micro- finance and its justification in Nigeria. It analyzes the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Micro-finance Policy and appraises its implications on the development of SME's in Nigeria. It then conclude by making some recommendations towards ensuring maximum impact of the policy on SME's.

THE NATURE OF MEDIUM, SMALL AND MICRO ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

The importance of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs), in any economy cannot be over-emphasized, especially when it comes to empowering and developing the micro economy. It has been observed that most developed countries built their development around the MSME sub-sector. Also, in developing nations across the world, these set of businesses accounts for over 50 per cent of the private workforce, as is the case in the United States where more than half of the nation's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is generated by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)².

An SME is defined as a company with more than 10 but less than 250 employees. In the case of the European Union, SMEs account for

¹ Dele Ojo, Growing The Economy Through Micro-Financing at pp 19-20 Business day, July 18th

² See Adewumi Olumide, Small Enterprises As a Nation's Economic Driving Force, Financial Standard, Monday, July 16, 2007 at p. 13.

99.8 per cent of all companies and gives account for 58 per cent of global working population while contributing about 30 per cent to the GDP. The sub-sector is an avenue for the employment generation, even industrial development and general economic growth but its very disturbing that in Nigeria, where over 93 per cent of the available enterprises falls within this category, little or nothing had been achieved in the area of developing and supporting these set of entrepreneurs who have dreaded to take the bull by the horn, and ventured into this laudable enterprises³.

MEETING THE CHALLENGES OF SMES IN NIGERIA

The structure and operation of a micro, small and medium enterprises plays a part in its level or rate of development and success.

The ownership structure of Smes is a factor that either increases or reduces the risk profile and by implication the price at which it could raise funds.

The typical Smes in Nigeria are closely owned entities. Mortality rate of Smes, in the developed countries could be as high as 20 to 50 percent of new small enterprises, an example being in the United States. In the developing world, it is more. These firms usually fail within the first one or two years of operation, and this problem is audibly evident in Nigeria, and this is due to the absence of partnership spirits; supposed partners in many Smes pursue individualistic goals at the expense of the overall interest of the Sme. It should be noted also that the over dependence on imported raw materials, machinery and spare parts is another strong impediment facing the Smes⁴.

The fact that Nigerians are enterprising does not in any way take away their shortcomings in the area of appropriate managerial skills. Due to inadequate capital and technical competence, entrepreneurs purchase obsolete and inefficient equipments thereby setting the stage for low level of productivity and poor product quality with serious consequences on market acceptability.

There has been concerted efforts and attempts in some settings to set up Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) in the time past toward aiding the economic development of businesses, and to give them a good leverage as regards funding. The idea of further enhancing the abilities of the enterprise was demonstrated in the establishment of the Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (Smeeis) to give the entrepreneurs a sound footing, making meaningful impact in the development of the economy through the issue of funding. The Smeeis idea was followed by other policies from the government like the microfinance policy and other intervention policies aimed at bridging the funding gap between the established businesses and the later⁵.

³ Adewumi Olumide, Ibid.

⁴ Adewumi Olumide, Ibid.

1. ⁵ The Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (Smes) as it was first called was introduced in 2001 with the primary aim of catering for the MSMEs where all banks were mandated to set aside 10 percent of their pre-tax profit (PBT) towards the scheme. It was a voluntary initiative of the Bankers committee which was approved at its 26th meeting held in December 2; 1999 in response to the federal government's concern and policy measures for the promotion of Smes as a vehicle for rapid industrialization, sustainable economic development, poverty alleviation and employment generation. However, the committee consisting of top executives of the apex bank, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), chief executives of banks in the country and other stakeholders had expressed disappointment over the low patronage of the fund, observing that only 30 per cent had actually been accessed

The policies of government in this regards had been commendable but the execution is faulty. Apart from Smeis, the Federal government in 2005 during the launching of the micro-finance policy mandated the other two-tiers of government, state and local government, to contribute 1 per cent of their budgets to the micro-finance institution for onward lending to the Smes, but this directive is yet to be implemented as at the present moment. However, the coming of the micro-finance policy vis-à-vis the micro-finance banks gives a sign of a silver lining across the sky with the hope that it will contribute immensely to the development of the sub-sector⁶.

THE CONCEPT OF MICROFINANCE

Microfinance refers to small-scale financial services -primarily credit and savings- provided to people who farm or fish or herd; who operate small enterprises or micro enterprises where goods are produced, recycled, repaired, or sold, who provide services; who work for wages or commissions; who gain income from renting out small amounts of land, vehicles, draft animals, or machinery and tools; and to other individuals and groups at the local levels of developing countries, both rural and urban. Many such households have multiple sources of income⁷. Savings services allow savers to store excess liquidity for future use and to obtain

by Smes as opposed to the targeted number. As at March 2007, out of the total fund of N39.1 billion pooled by the banks for Smes, only N 16billion which translates to about 41 percent has been accessed by Smes. The idea of equity funding under the scheme as a driving force for massive growth is a means of providing equity capital for businesses instead of debt or bank finance, it's a form of long term investment fir the MSMEs spread across the country, that has the potential to develop into mega economic contributors.

⁶ See Adewumi Olumide, Ibid

⁷ Some analysts have restricted microfinance to narrower definitions. Thus the term is often used to refer to those who work in the informal sector of the economy.

While most microfinance serves the informal sector, the definition used here is broader and includes financial services to poor employees of the formal sector as well. Such employees can, in fact, be poorer than those in the informal sector. For example, a 1987-88 study of 500 urban informal sector workers (pedicab drivers, scavengers recycling waste materials, and peddlers selling food or garments) in Jakarta, Indonesia, found that the average daily income of those surveyed was higher than the salaries of most of Jakarta's formal sector employees (as reported by the Indonesian Bureau of Statistics). Additional household income was not considered in either case (CPIS 1988a). Other uses of the term microfinance sometimes have the effect of restricting its meaning to specifics, such as village lending programmes or group lending methodologies. However, microfinance is used here to refer generally to all types of financial services provided to low-income households and enterprises. See generally: (1) Adams, Dale W., and Delbert

A. Fitchett. 1992, *Informal Finance in Low-Income Countries*. Boulder, Colo.:

Westview Press. (2) Adams, Dale W., and Robert C. Vogel. 1986. "Rural Financial Market in Low-income Countries: Recent Controversies and Lessons." *World Development* 14 (4): 477-87, (3) Adams, Dale, W., and J.D. Von Pischke. 1992, "Micro enterprises Credit Programs: Déjà vu". *World Development* 20 (10): 1463-70, (4) Agafonoff, Alex, and d. Wilkins. 1994. "Developing Financial Instrument to Support Poverty-Oriented Financial Institutions- Banco Solidario S.A. Opportunity International, Chicago, III, (5) Bass, Jacqueline, and Katrena Henderson. 2000. "The Micro finance Experience with Savings Mobilization." USAID Micro-enterprises Best Practices Project. Weidman Associates and Development Alternatives, Washington, D.C., (6) Berenbach, Shari and Craig Churchill. 1997. "The Regulation and Supervision of Micro-finance Institutions:

returns on their investments. Credit services enable the use of anticipated income for current investment or consumption. Overall, microfinance services can help low-income people reduce risk, improve management, raise productivity, obtain higher returns on investments, increase their incomes, and improve the quality of their lives and those of their dependents.⁸

Such services are rarely accessible through the formal financial sector, however. Credit is widely available from informal commercial moneylenders but typically, as will be documented, at very high cost to the borrowers - especially poor borrowers. Banks generally assume that providing small loans and deposit services would be unprofitable. It is widely believed-wrongly, as will be demonstrated-that the cost of delivering small scale financials services at the local level is too high for non-subsidized institutions and that the informal financial market satisfies demand. NGOs and other nonbank financial institutions have led the way in developing appropriate credit methodologies for low-income borrowers. But with few exceptions, these institutions are able to operate only on a very small scale⁹.

The problem is exacerbated by the limited influence of the poor people who require microfinance. They are usually unable to inform formal markets about their creditworthiness or about their demand for savings services and loans. Accordingly, services are not provided. Those who hold the power do not understand the demand; those who understand the demand do not hold the power¹⁰.

There are differences among countries and regions in the availability of microfinance services and in the level of unmet demand for these services. There are also differences in demand among small businesses, microenterprises, farmers, labourers, low-income salaried employees, and others. Common to nearly all parts of the developing world, however, is a lack of commercial microfinance institutions-shortcoming that unnecessarily limits the options and lowers the financial security of poor people throughout the world¹¹.

But this pattern is changing. The microfinance revolution is emerging in many counties around the world. As it is used here, this term refers to the large-scale, profitable provision of microfinance services-small savings and loans-to economically active poor people by sustainable financial institutions. These services are provided by competing institutions at the local level-near the homes and workplaces of the clients-in both rural and urban areas. Financial services delivered at the local level refer to those provided to people living in villages and other types of rural settlements and to people living in low-income neighbourhoods in semiurban or

Experience from Latin America, Asia, and Africa." Occasional Paper 1. Micro-finance Network, Washington, D.C, (7) Grameen Foundation 1998. Grameen Connections: The Newsletter of Grameen Foundation USA 1 (1): 12 (8) Gulli, Hege. 1998. Microfinance and Poverty: Questioning the Conventional Wisdom.

Washington D. C.: Inter-American Development Bank (9) Otero, Maria. 1998. "Types of Owners fro Micro-finance Institutions". In C. Churchill, ed., Moving Microfinance Forward: Ownership, Competition and Control of Microfinance Institutions, Washington, D.C. MicroFinance Network. (10) Otero, Maria, and Elisabeth Rhyne, eds. 1994. The New World of Microenterprise Finance: Building Healthy Financial Institutions for the Poor. West Hartford. Conn. Kumarian Press.

⁸ Marguerite S. Robinson, 2001, The Micro Finance Revolution: Sustainable Finance for the Poor: The World Bank/Open Society Institute at p. 9.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Ibid.

urban areas. Large scale as used here means covered by multiple institutions of millions of clients; or, for small countries or middle-and high-income counties with low demand, outreach to a significant portion of the microfinance market. Profitability means covering all costs and risks without subsidy and returning a profit to the institution¹²

In aggregate, commercial microfinance institutions can provide outreach to a significant segment of their country's poor households. In a few countries this has already occurred; in others it is at various stages of progress. This book is about the microfinance revolution-the principles on which it is based, the dynamics of its processes, the speed of its progress, and its role in economic and social development.¹³

JUSTIFICATION FOR MICRO-FINANCE INSTITUTIONS

One of the main justifications for the introduction of Micro-finance Policy in Nigeria is the failure of past pro-poor project of successive governments. Before the conception and implementation of this policy in Nigeria several attempts have been made in the past introducing those policies aimed at poverty alleviation. In 1972, the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) was introduced alongside the Nigerian Agricultural and Co-operative Bank (NACB), which later became Nigerian Agricultural Co-operative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB). This was followed in 1976 by Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) and later the Green Revolution which was introduced by the regime of Alhaji Shehu Shagari. General Buhari's regime came and introduced "Back to Land Programme," which other states copied and tagged "Schools to Land Programme" or "Graduates Farming Scheme."¹⁴ In 1986, Babangida's government established the DFRRRI (Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure) to accelerate rural development. Under this regime, various projects such as the Peoples Banks of Nigeria and Community Banks of Nigeria were introduced.

Others include Better Life Programme (BLP) or Better Life for Rural Women and the Family Support Programme (FSP) and Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP)¹⁵. Most of the pro-poor projects of these successive governments were colossal failures, No sooner had a regime been terminated than a programme cancelled. Furthermore, lip services were only paid to the implementation to these programmes.¹⁶

Another factor is the weak institutional capacity of existing community banks. This weakness is largely due to incompetent management, weak internal control and lack of deposit insurance. This is in addition to the weak capital base of the existing institutions especially, community banks. Only 75 out of 600 community banks whose financial statements were approved by CBN in 2005 had up to 20 million shareholders fund unimpaired by losses.

A further reason is the existence of a huge unserved market. The average banking density in Nigeria is one bank office to 32, 700 inhabitants. In the rural areas it is 1:57,000 i.e. less than 2 per cent of rural households have accesses to financial services.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ See Bukky Olajide, Micro-finance As A Global Economic Growth Strategy, The Quardian, Wednesday, June 20, 2007 at pp 27-28

¹⁵ See Bakky Olajide, Micro-finance As A Global Economic Growth Strategy, The Quardian, Wednesday, June 20, 2007 at pp 27-28

¹⁶ Ibid.

Other reasons include the need to economically empowered the poor, generate chiployment and reduce poverty reduction¹⁷, the need for increased savings opportunity.

Non or low utilization of SMEEIS funds is another major reason for the introduction of the Micro-finance Policy. As at December 2005 only 30 per cent of SMEEIS fund of about N40 billion has been utilized 10 per cent of this fund is meant id meant for micro credit but could not be utilized due to lack of an appropriate framework and confidence in the existing institutions that would have served the purpose.

Again the likelihood that MSE's might not enjoy much patronage by mega banks that would emerge in the post consolidation era in Nigeria also necessitated the emergence of microfinance policies since non of the reasons stated for the consolidation policy by the Central Bank made reference to MSE's. The consolidation of 89 banks that existed prior to December 31, 2005 to 25 mega banks with minimum paid up capital of N25 billion also raises concern as to the ability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to access banking services in a post consolidated mega banking environment. Banking consolidation through mergers and acquisition has always been propelled either by the regulatory authority or market forces.¹⁸

In Europe and America consolidation of banks were stimulated largely by the need to eliminate weak or problem banks and market forces 10 leverage on changes in telecommunication and information technology and removal of legal and regulatory barriers to national and international linkage¹⁹. In Nigeria while it appears that the most compelling reason for banking consolidation was the need to eliminate the weak and problem banks. The Central Bank justified the reform on²⁰:

- (1) The need to enhance the international ranking/compatibility of Nigerian banks
- (2)The need to improve the ability of Nigerian banks to play active roles in International banking and large ticket financing including management of Nigerian external reserves²¹
- (3)The need to improve the resilience of Nigerian banks and redress the tendency/vulnerability to distress or failure²²
- (4) The need to improve the flow of resources to the productive sectors of the economy (especially, the real sector and services)²³.
- (5) The need to streamline/improve banking supervision/ examination functions of the apex bank thereby eliminating or reducing opportunities for sharp practices.²⁴

¹⁷ Only about I'm people are employed by 6498 small and medium enterprises according to stall and medium industry survey in 2004.

¹⁸ See Bolade Agboola, Prospects and Challenges of SME's and Micro-finance in Post Consolidation Banks, *The Guardian*, Monday, June 25, 2007 at p. 23. See also Olugbemi Fatula, 2005, *The Implications of Recapitalisation for Consolidation, Good Corporate Governance and Universal Banking in Nigeria*; *Igbinedion University Law Journal*, Volume 3, September 2005 at pp. 21-40 particularly at p. 23.

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Ibid

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

It is apparent from the above that access to banking services by micro, small and medium enterprises is not one of the reasons for consolidating Nigerian banks into 25 mega banks.²⁵

At a global level, majority of the people in less developed countries lack access to finances or savings which further enhanced vicious cycle of poverty. The people have limited capacity to invest in capital, productivity is restricted, income is inhibited while domestic savings are either low or nil, and any increase in productivity is prevented. An access to financial services will open several avenues which will eventually break the cycle of poverty. The sources and consequences of entrepreneurial activities will therefore become financially and environmentally sustainable. The conscious and concerted effort of micro-entrepreneur aided by accessibility to micro credit would give rise to an improved environment through employment creation, increase in income and investment as well as speedy poverty alleviation. Others are development of rural areas, reduction in insecurity of life and property, healthy living, improving infrastructure and enhancing quality environment and so on.²⁶

Another justification for the Introduction of Micro-finance in Nigeria is that the concept has become popular having been introduced and implemented in other jurisdiction. In India, the basic principle guiding the funding of small enterprises is that the government regard them as the eggs that hatch big business. The government started giving adequate incentives by supporting small businesses with bulk purchasing of their products at retailing -term both for the domestic market and for exports.

To facilitate their access to bank credits, the government issued LPOs for them and while banks accept such contracts with small ones, big business must bid 15 per cent less than small businesses for them to supply government needs. Payments are promptly made to the small businesses and this encourage their growth²⁷

In Brazil, apart from heavy funding and subsidies, the government provides infrastructure in an area while encouraging the cluster of industries. The Sinos Valley Shoe Company in Brazil grew out of this arrangement of cluster industries. In fact, it is a company like this that made Brazil the world's third largest producer of shoes. In Latin America, microfinance commenced in 1980s with the advent of social-driven. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) thereby make loan available to poor micro entrepreneurs funded largely by grants and soft loans from donors and government²⁸. By early 1990, some large commercial banks such as Banco de Credito of Peru and Banco de Trabajo of Peru had fully entered into micro lending. Professor Yunus established the Grameen Bank of Bangladesh in 1976 when he lent \$27 to 42 women. From 1983 when it was established it has granted a total of 6.6 million micro loans. The K-Rep Bank Limited of Kenya has outstanding portfolio of almost \$20 million with 42,000 active borrowers and about \$12 million savings despite. The micro finance was, however, still a market leader despite strong competition because it offer attractive products and services. K-Rep's loan products are evenly distributed between micro credit (51 per cent) and small business or

²⁵ Ibid. See Ogujiuba, K.K. Ohuche, F. K and Adenuga, A.O. Credit Availability to Small and Medium scale Enterprises in Nigeria: Importance of New Capital Base for Banks -Backgrounds and Issues, Unpublished Working Chapter of AIAE 2004

²⁶ Ibid

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Ibid

consumer loan. It also has a computerized system that assists in performing disbursements and collections at filed offices²⁹

Also, the bank offers safe custody and foreign exchange services and considering introducing money transfer while considering the introduction of Automated Teller Machines, as they became increasingly popular for both banks and clients in Kenya. As a long-term goal, the bank also plans to introduce Internet and cell phone banking, which would further improve its services and costs. It also has a good risk management policy, which the board constantly reviews and adopts to the prevailing environment to ensure optimum mitigation of risk.

Again, Micro-enterprise works best in countries where the political, economic and social environments allow small entrepreneurs to succeed beyond the level of basic survival. To effectively address the problems of today's poor, there was a need to understand much more about the mechanisms that perpetuated their poverty and the processes by which those mechanisms could be improved³⁰. Robust economic growth cannot be achieved without putting in place well focused programmes to reduce poverty by empowering people through increased access to factors of production, especially credit. The latent capacity of the poor for entrepreneurship would be significantly enhanced through the provision of micro-finance services to enable them engage in economic activities and be more self-reliant; increase employment opportunities, enhanced household income, and create wealth.

Furthermore, Micro-finance is about providing financial services to the poor who are traditionally not served by the conventional financial institutions. Three features distinguish micro-finance from other formal financial products. These are: the smallness of loans advanced and or savings collected; the absence of assets-based collateral and the simplicity of operations. Micro-finance is the progenitor of local private sector development. It feeds small and medium enterprise developments thus propelling the growth of micro-enterprise but also fueling the expansion of suppliers and vertical infrastructures needed by larger businesses. Because micro-finance creates increased wealth for low-income individuals, it also creates new consumers and markets for businesses of all sizes. Micro-finance increasingly supports purchasing living space, home improvement and home building in slums through special savings and loan products. It generates wealth for slum dwellers, enabling them to obtain improved housing.

The last reason is the role and contributions of SME's to economic and social development. Notable contributions of SME to the socioeconomic development of their host economy include the transformation of traditional or indigenous industry through training of semi-skilled workers, stimulation of indigenous entrepreneurship and technology, promotion of balanced regional development, creation of jobs especially, self - employment, redistribution of wealth and income, utilization of local resources in the form of backward and forward linkages, dispersal and diversification of economic activities and mobilization of savings.

Unlike multinational firms, SMEs disperse economic activities over a wide geographical area of the country, and by so doing, provide a variety of choice goods to the populace, thus improving the standards of living of the citizens. In this way, SMEs serve as a strategy for checking rural-urban immigration by reducing the gap in the developmental and income levels between urban centre and rural areas. SMEs therefore, also serve as a tool for regional economic balancing. Other identified vital role of SMEs include the utilization of local raw materials and linkages with large industries, mobilization of domestic savings and the provision of training group for entrepreneurs. In view of the contributions of SME's to national

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Ibid

economies, stimulating sustained investment in the sector as become one of the core economic issues in modern world³¹

THE ANATOMY OF CBN'S MICRO-FINANCE POLICY

Micro financing is very important to micro enterprises and may not even be able to function without it. It was in realization of the importance of Micro-finance to Micro-enterprises that the Micro-finance Policy, Regulatory and Supervisory Framework for Nigeria was launched on December 15th 2005³². The policy provides for the setting up of micro-finance banks to provide financial services for poor and low- income groups so as to bring them into the economic mainstream of the nation. It was expected that by enabling the poor to engage in such economic activities, employment would be generated, earnings will be increased and their standard of living would be improved. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) as the driver of the implementation of the policy, had sensitized would- be investors in micro-finance banks and the converting community banks on the requirements for licensing micro-finance banks as well as procedures and requirements for con version to micro-finance banks³³.

According to CBN, a micro-finance policy which recognizes the existing informal institutions and brings them within the supervisory purview of the CBN would not only enhance monetary stability, but also expand the financial infrastructure of the country to meet the financial requirements of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Such a policy would create a vibrant micro-finance sub-sector that would be adequately integrated into the mainstream of the national financial system and provide the stimulus for growth and development. It would also harmonize operating standards and provide a strategic platform for the evolutions, promote appropriate regulation, supervision and adoption of best practices.

The policy provides an alternati ve banking arrangement for the small businesses. Through the policy, micro-finance banks, with the mandate to attend to the needs of small and micro-enterprise, will be established. According to the policy, to get a loan from a micro-finance bank (MFB), 'one must have a monthly income of not more than the monthly per capital in come of Nigeria or twice the minimum wage, which ever is high. The beneficiary must have a total productive assets including those arising from loans, but excluding the cost of loan) of not more than N500,000. Also to qualify for assistance, one must be self- employed, and between the ages of 18 and 60.

According to the guidelines, a Micro-finance Bank (MFB), unless otherwise stated, shall be construed to mean any company licensed to carry on the business of providing micro-finance services, such as savings, loans, domestic fund transfer and other financial services that are needed by the economically- active enterprises, to conduct or expand their businesses as defined by the guidelines.

³¹ See Central Bank of Nigeria, Micro Finance Policy, Regulatory and Supervisory Framework for Nigeria, (Abuja, December 2005 (hereafter called "Micro Finance Policy"). See also, Baunmback C.M, Small Business, Small Business Management, (Prentice Hall Inc, Englewood Cliff, 1983); Audretsch, David B, Innovation and Indistry Evolution (Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press, 1995); Nugent, J. B. & Yhee S., Small and Medium Enterprises in Korea: Achievements, Constraints and Policy Issues. (World Bank Institute, 2001) 2., Ojo T.A., Small and Medium Enterprises Development and SMIES: Effective Implementation Strategies (CIBN Press Lagos)

³² Ibid

³³ Ibid

The loans are meant for poor person³⁴(s) operating a micro-enterprises³⁵ requiring micro loan³⁶ to operate and expand. The specific objectives of this micro finance policy are to: (1) to make financial services accessible to a large segment of the potentially-productive population which otherwise would have little or no access to financial services, (2) promote synergy and mainstreaming of the informal sub-sector into the national financial system, (3) enhance services delivery by micro-finance institutions to micro, small and medium entrepreneur, (4) contribute to rural transformation; and (5) promote linkage programmes between universal/development banks, specialized institutions and micro-finance banks.

Based on the objectives listed above, the targets of the policy are:

(1) to cover the majority of the poor but economically active population by 2020 thereby creating million of jobs and reducing poverty, (2) to increase the share of micro credits as a percentage of total credit to the economy from 0.9 per cent in 2005 to at least 20 per cent by 2020; and the share of micro credit as a percentage of GDP from 0.2 per cent in 2005 to at least 5 per cent in 2020, (3) to promote the participation of at least two-thirds of the states and local governments in micro credit financing by 2020, (4) to eliminate gender disparity by improving women's access to financial services by 5 per cent annually; and (5) to increase the number of linkages among universal banks, development banks specialized financial institutions and micro-finance banks by 10 percent annually.

CRITIQUE OF THE CBN'S MICRO-FINANCE POLICY

Arguably, the single greatest challenge of the approved MFBs in the country is the widespread apathy of their targeted clientele. Indeed, to many of those in the economically active poor and low income categories, the question is? How will microfinance banks succeed when similar institutions like Peoples Bank of Nigeria and Community Banks failed? There is a world of difference between the new MFBs and previous institutions like peoples and community banks. And the differences guarantee the success of the MFBs imitative.

³⁴ A poor person is defined as one who has meager means of sustenance or livelihood and whose total income in a year is less than the minimum taxable limit set out in the law relating to income tax.

³⁵ A micro enterprise is a business that requires micro credit/ loans to operate. Its operation and management are often built around the sole owner- micro entrepreneur.

The micro entrepreneur usually works alone or provides employment for a few people; typically the immediate family members. The enterprise does not often require formal registration to start. The management and accounting requirement of the business are usually very simple and flexible. Generally, micro entrepreneurs work informally with or without license or formal records of their activities or earnings. The scope of micro enterprises typically include primary production and value added processing and distribution trade.

³⁶ A micro loan is a facility granted to an individual borrower or a group of borrowers whose principal business include the production of goods and sales of foods and services. The Maximum Principal amount does not exceed N500, 000 or as may be reviewed from time to time by the CBN. Generally, micro- loan is granted to the operators of micro- enterprises such as peasant farmers, artisans, fishermen and rural women, Senior Citizens, salaries and non-salaries workers in the formal and informal sectors. The said loans are usually unsecured, but typically granted on the basis of the applicants' character and the combined cash flow of the business and household. Ordinarily the tenure of micro loan is 180 days (6 months). However, in the case of crop with a longer gestation period, a maximum tenure of twelve (12 months) is permitted.

Some include the increased capitalization of MFBs, the enhanced skill and competence of their operators, their embrace of best practices, international partnership and better technology and continuous support by CBN among others.

Indeed, whereas the apex bank fixed N20 million as the minimum capitalization for MFBs wishing to operate in a local government area and one billion for those to operate state wide, only 75 out of the about 600 community banks whose accounts were approved by the CBN last year had up to N20 million shareholders funds unimpaired by losses. Also, even at marketing and customer relations level, the qualification level of skills and competence of employees in the new MFBs cannot be compared to those in the community banks. And at the management level too, the difference is also very clear. Investment in technology by the MFBs and the adoption of best practices in their operations and the existences of international partners and the support of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)³⁷.

No doubt, the success of the MFBS will depend largely on the strategies they employed to ensure a successful operation. Nigeria could learn from the Bangladesh Grameen Bank in this regard.

However, increased awareness by MFBs on available services, so as to attract higher patronage, remains a major challenge. The interest rate, put at between five and 10 per cent, depending on the transaction, is comparatively okay.

WAY FORWARDS³⁸

The establishment of microfinance banks has become imperative to serve the following purposes: (1) Provide diversified, affordable and dependable financial services to the active poor in a timely and competitive manner that would enable them to undertake and develop long term, sustainable entrepreneurial activities; (2) Create savings for intermediation; (3) Create employment opportunities and increase the productivity of the active poor in the country thereby increasing the individual household income and uplifting their standard of living; (4) Enhance participation of the poor in the socio-economic development and resource allocation process; (5) Provide veritable avenues for the administration of the micro credit programmes of government and high net worth individuals on a no-recourse basis. In

³⁷ In its efforts to create necessary awareness on MFBs. CBN listed some institutional arrangement put in place to ensure MFBs success. These include the following: (1) Independently managed Microfinance Development Fund to provide wholesale funds, refinance facilities and other services of support for the financial activities of MFBs and microfinance institutions; (2) Certification programme for staff and management of MFBs to provide adequate knowledge on microfinance practice, enhance operational activities and ensure that right persons manage the MFBs; (3) Rating agencies, to provide institutional assessment of MFBs and other institutions; (4) Credit bureaux, to provide credit information on microfinance clients in support of the credit and other decision making processes of the MFBs; (5) Apex association of the MFBs to ensure compliance with standards and best practices.

³⁸ See Lucky Fiapa, When Attention Shifted to Effective Jumpstarting of SMEs, Business Cover Story, Thisday, The Sunday Newspaper, November 26, 2006 at pp 28-29. Being the summary report of a two day conference of policy makers, financial experts, small business operators as well as other stakeholders held in November 2006 at Abuja under the auspices of NEPAD Business Group, Nigeria to brainstorm on how get the country's SMEs started and contribute meaningfully to the economy.

particular, this policy ensures that state government shall dedicate an amount of not less than 1 percent of their annual budgets for the on-lending activities of micro-finance banks in favour of their residents³⁹.

Aside the strategies stipulated by the policy which were developed from the policy objectives and targets, the operators of micro finance must ensure a need for training and capacity building. Aside the proper policy and regulatory framework the other challenge was to continuously increase the skills of both supervising and the operating institutions so as to ensure that their practise were enhanced and prudentially managed. The experience of other countries like Bangladesh, Philip pine, Kenya, Uganda, Indonesia could be leveraged.

There is equally the need for strategic marketing of micro finance⁴⁰, the creation of an enabling policy environment⁴¹ and sound macroeconomic policies⁴², investment in rural infrastructure and human services⁴³, consolidation of concept⁴⁴ and the attraction of a donor support⁴⁵.

³⁹ See Toba Agboola, Micro-finance Banks to SMEs' Rescue, The Nation, Wednesday, November 29, 2006 at p 33.

⁴⁰ Understanding and appreciation of micro finance must be spread to all the stakeholders. All the microfinance banks, rural dwellers, upcoming entrepreneur and the general public must be adequately and consistently be informed of its modus operandi. The idea is to avail everybody the opportunity to buy into the scheme.

⁴¹ The key to building on enabling environment is maintenance of stable and growing economy and extension of the legal and regulatory framework to enhance the capacity of the supervisory authority, that is, CBN to effectively supervise and enforce prudential guideline on several micro finance institutions that may spring up.

⁴² This is necessary to compliment the efficiency and effectiveness of the legal and regulatory framework in the development of rural financial markets which requires sound monetary and fiscal policies which will result in macroeconomic stability with low and stable inflation. Extra-budgetary expenditures must be minimized to ensue price stability. In this way, micro enterprise will be able to realize their aim with modes projections and forecasts.

⁴³ There should be a paradigm shift in the budgetary planning and allocation of the Federal Government in favour of developing infrastructure in rural areas. There is need to invest adequately in rural infrastructure and human services especially in the area of providing safe drinking water, roads, electricity, telephone services, health and education. This will put an end to rural -urban drift. Subsequently, the rural areas will be transformed and be made more habitable

⁴⁴ The government need to consolidate on the new micro finance policy to achieved its expected goals

⁴⁵ Concerted efforts should be made to attract the support of the donor agencies for micro finance institutional building. However, whatever donation received should be prudentially guided and be directed to the right quarters in order to derive the expected benefit, that is, growth and expansion of economic activities. Micro insurance must be provided for the protection of minor perils. "The vital idea here is to avert risk, keep the micro entrepreneur away from risks that may scare them off the road to wealth creating". In looking for a new opportunity for growth and prosperity, increasing economic growth and individual prosperity through economic freedom must be core goals of development. Economic assistance could improve economic growth only in good policy environment, while the economic futures of developing countries lay predominantly in their own hand through policies that they choose to adopt and enforce long-term policy reform could no be forced upon them.

The micro- finance banks will be expected to go beyond the community banks by offering all banking transactions expected in any bank branch i.e. loans, deposits, money transfers and insurance. What should separate them is that their clients are so small that their business will not be attractive to the conventional banks. They should strive to generate returns that is superior to what large banks would. They must evolve into serious and viable business by selecting their clients on the basis of merit rather than cronyism or bribery which most families and state banks were guilty of in the past. They have to make conscious efforts to protect their deposits and attract new ones. They are to create a large body of people with viable economic ventures, who will demand decent services the satisfaction of which will promote their growth. Attention must be paid to the core areas that determine success of most financial institutions. These are: (1) culture⁴⁶, Products⁴⁷, Funding⁴⁸, Cost of operation⁴⁹.

There are so many challenges facing the scheme of micro financing in Nigeria, and the world at large. The biggest challenge for any lender institution, whether it is commercial, universal, micro-finance institution or co-operative, is always recovery of loans. Every step taken, in terms of designing the structure, must therefore be geared towards ensuring loan recovery. Group methodology for instance which ensures that borrowers put some level of pressure on each other to ensure that they redeem.

Payment instalmentally in small bits, short repayment of say one week schedule could be employed. Clients could also be made to undergo free training before accessing the credit. The other challenge is the issue of funding. Micro-finance is at its infancy in Africa and Nigeria. The Grammen Bank's experience in Bangladesh started with the group concept- informal lending to the poor. It started to assist landless people in Bangladesh to access credit, which could not be obtained through the formal commercial banks credit facilities. The program was successful because the groups were cohesive (landless) and voluntarily formed. The program has since been linked to formal micro credit model. It operates using the modality of collective guarantees, close supervision and peer pressure from other members of the Grammen group. The model had been quite successful as a bank for the poor and as a social movement based on principles of awareness and training, which has facilitated active participation of poor. Nigeria could study and adapt this model⁵⁰.

⁴⁶ They must transform from charity into proper business.

⁴⁷ They must align to global financial system in rendering financial services. They must go beyond credit

⁴⁸ Private equity must complement or replace government aids multilateral and donor funds,

⁴⁹ Micro- finance tends to be labour intensive and operate like private banking for wealthy people. It should operate like a retail bank and information technology must be good enough to reduce personal cost, See Bolade Agboola, op cite.

⁵⁰ See generally, (1) Rhyne, Elisabeth. Forthcoming. *Mainstreaming: How Lending to the Poor Began, Grew and Came of Age in Belivia*. Bloomfield, Conn.: Kumarian Press.(2) Rhyne, Elisabeth, and Richard Rosenberg. 1998. "A Donor's Guide to Supporting Mcirofinance Institutions". CGAP Occasional Paper. World Bank, Consultative Group to Assist the Poorest, Washington, D.C. (3) Rhyne, Elisabeth, and Linda S. Rotblatt. 1994. *What Makes Them Tick? Exploring the Anatomy of Major Micro enterprise Finance Organisation*. Monograph 9. Someville, Mass.: ACCION International. (4) Rhyne, Elisabeth, 1997a. "Introducing Savings in Micro credit Institutions: When and How?" CGAP Focus Note 8. Consultative Group to Assist the Poorest, World Bank, Washington, D.C.(5)Rhyne, Elisabeth 1998a.

Mcirofinance: The Paradigm Shift from Credit Delivery to Sustainable Financial Intermediation". In Carl K. Eicher and John M. Staatz, eds. *Agricultural Development in the Third World*. 3d ed. Baltimore, Md: The Johns Hopkins University Press. Reprinted with minor

There the need for the development of a credit data bureau in Nigeria in its effort to develop economically. Nigeria is predominantly a cash economy with limited access to credit by individuals and small businesses. The credit market in Nigeria is under-developed and performance of credit portfolio of banks who are primary providers of credit in Niger is sub-optimal. An industry non-performing loan is significant Non Performing Loans to total loans is equal to 26 percent in 2004, 16 percent in 2005 less than 10 percent in 2006). High rate of credit delinquency has significant negative bottom line impact in the performance of providers of credit. While several factors are responsible for this trend, a substantial portion of loan, losers are attributable to serial defaulters, who exploit the absence of reliable and integrated credit inform multiple lending institutions with the intention to default.

The absence of consolidated credit information has also implied that large numbers of consumer and small business borrowers are excluded from the credit market. Less than 5 percent of bank customer are borrowing customers. Banks have been constrained in their ability to make informed decisions on the credit worthiness of non-corporate customers who have limited and often times unreliable financial information. Recent economic reform in Nigeria including better capitalized banks and insurance companies are driving a shift in the industry landscape. There is increase focus on retail banking credit cards have been introduced, microfinance and consumer lending/ finance with consumer loan products make it imperative that there is a reliable credit data on individuals and organizations for information based

additions in Mwangi S Kinyeni, Robert C. Weiland. and J.D. Von Psichke, eds 1998, Strategic Issues in Micro finance . Aldershot, England: Aldershot. (6) Rock, Rachel. 1997, "Bolivia". In C. Churchill, ed, "The Regulation and Supervision of Mcirofinance Institutions: Case Studies" Occasional Paper 2. Microfinance Network., Washington, D.C. (7) Rock Rachel, and Maria Otero, eds 1997. From Margin to Mainstream: The Regualtions and Supervision of Mcirofinance. Monograph 11. Someville, Mass.: ACCION International. (8) Sugianto, and Marguerite S. Robinson. 1998. "Sustainable Microfinance as Developed by the Bank Rakyat Indonesia" Jakarta. Sugianto, Satriyo Purnomo, and Marguerite S. Roinson. 1993 Bunga Rampai Penbiavaan Pertanian. Jakarta: Institute Bankir Indonesia (9) Versluysen, Eugene 1999. Defying the Odds: Banking for the Poor. West Harford, Com.: Kumarian Press. (10) Women's World Banking. 1996. Institution Building in Microfinance: Lessons from Funders and Practitioners. New York Women's World Banking and United Nations Development Programme. (11) Women's World Banking. 1996a, "A Worldwide Inventory of Microfinance Institutions. " World Bank Stistainable Banking with the Poor Project, Washington, D.C. (12) Women World Banking. 1997 a. " An Inventory of Microfinance Institutions in Asia and the Pacific." Sustainable Banking with the Poor project, Washington D.C (13) Women World Banking, 2000. Microfinance Systems: Designing Quality Financial Services for the Poor. London and New York: Zed Books. (14) Wright, Graham A. N., and others. 199. "Vulnerability, Risks, Assets and Empowerment -The Impact of Microfinance on Poverty Alleviation, Final Report "MicroSave -Africa and Uganda Women's Finance Trust, Rampala. Uganda. (15) Yaron, Jacob, 1992a. Assessing Development Finance Institutions: A Public Interest Analysis. World Bank Discussion Paper 174, Washington, D.C. (16) Yaron, Jacob, 1992b Successful Rural Finance Institutions. World Bank Discussion Paper 150. Washington, D.C. See also Marguerite S. Robinson, 2001, The Micro-finance Revolution: Sustainable Finance for the Poor, The World Bank/ Open Society Institute.

lending decisions and management. Credit reference bureau will transform Nigeria's credit industry by providing much needed information to credit providers as a powerful tool for enabling better informed lending decisions and loan management.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are significant business growth opportunities for banks, but significant risk of bad debt losses as some owners of SMEs might not be honest. Many are not experienced borrowers and many over commit themselves and some are incompetent managers. Debt recovery action through the courts is difficult. SME owners are resourceful given an opportunity they will deal with multiple lenders.

Credit reference data bureau will help to sort bad credit applicants from good ones, saves time spent on borrower evaluations, reduces the - cost of screening, prices loans adequately in accordance with the risk of the borrowers and reduces overall system risk.

The benefits of such a bureau to the banks include: (1) improved efficiency of credit approval and processing; (2) objective credit decision; (3) appropriate risk based pricing fraud prevention; (4) enablement of evolution of value added credit products and decline in loan losses; (5) increased market penetration⁵¹

A credit data bureau will establish a credible database of aggregated information of credit status and behaviour about borrowers in Nigeria to enable credit providers to make the critical move towards informing lending. The bureau will serve the consumers, small businesses and commercial lending segments, by maintaining a database of comprehensive up -to-date information on borrowers and providing Credit Informed Report (CIRs) to subscribers⁵².

CONCLUSION

There no doubt that the policy, if well implemented could launch Nigeria on its way to joining the league of nations that have become developed. There is great expectation that money at affordable interest rates with liberal terms will be available to support the real sector in new ways with a positive effect on Gross Domestic Product growth and employment. Past programmes and projects failed because they were based on faulty philosophies, corruption, lack of commitment on the side of both the government and the beneficiaries and government bureaucracy. It becomes important to tighten the loose knots and fulfill the conditionalities for exploiting the numerous opportunities of micro-finances⁵³.

Although the banks through the Smeeis project have been able to inject some equity into MSMEs, and indirectly the economic growth of the nation, the coming of the micro-finance policy has created another opportunity for the banks to play an active and pivotal role in the development of MSMEs through the establishments of micro-finance institutions to focus on MSMEs. The banks can participate by setting up micro-finance banks of their own, and they can diversify into venture capital companies to leverage on their huge capital base based on the success of their recent recapitalisation, indirectly supporting the growth of small businesses⁵⁴.

Like in developed countries, there should be dedicated banks for small businesses as well as agencies that are functioning, not just in names.

⁵¹ See Rajesh Mirchandani, Credit Reference Company Will Transform Nigeria's Credit Industry, *Businessday*, Monday June 25 2007 at p 3.

⁵² Ibid

⁵³ Ibid

⁵⁴ See dewumi Olumide, Ibid.

The agency should function at the federal level as an independent body responsible for the national policies, programme relating to the sub-sector with its own budget under the close supervision of the National Assembly.

This effort should also be duplicated at the state level. The government should encourage banks to set up joint venture capital businesses with experts to handle the investment of their increasing funds, as venture capitalists will actively work with the SMEs management by contributing their experience in business knowledge gained from helping other firms with similar challenges. Undoubtedly, vibrant and efficient SMEs is a vital and desirable tool for the overall economic development of the country⁵⁵.

⁵⁵ Ibid.